

TOWARDS ACHIEVING SDG 5: A STUDY ON THE BARRIERS AND CHALLENGES IN THE ECONOMIC, SOCIAL, AND POLITICAL ENGAGEMENT OF MUSLIM WOMEN IN BALIGATAN, ILAGAN CITY

Ma. Allycia Concepcion A. Tumaneng, Jonel L. Santiago

BA Political Science
Isabela State University-Cauayan

ABSTRACT

Sustainable Development Goal 5 primarily concerns gender equality and empowering all women and girls. It was established in response to the numerous criticisms of advancing gender-specific agendas. The road to equal engagement has been extremely long. Despite a slight increase in numbers over the years, women constantly face discrimination and barriers, such as cultural and societal standards, as well as access to financial resources, that prevent them from fully participating in decision-making roles. Up until now, Muslim women have endured a variety of discrimination and injustices that lead to marginalization. Knowing these, this study sought to determine the barriers and challenges in Muslim women's economic, social, and political engagement in Baligatan, Ilagan City, Isabela. The researchers employed a qualitative descriptive approach and interviewed the respondents to gather all the necessary data. The data collection complied with the ethical considerations. Based on the data gathered, it was found that Muslim women in Baligatan have limited engagement in economic, social, and political affairs. The barriers and challenges that restrain Muslim women from engaging in various affairs are discrimination, patriarchal practices, inadequate opportunities for sources of living, lack of confidence, and lack of knowledge. The researchers also concluded that there were no existing activities and practices in the Muslim community to achieve SDG 5. However, "Madrasah" and "Ilagan Association for Women" (ILAW) emerged as support programs that empower Muslim women in the city of Ilagan. However, these programs were still not enough for their empowerment.

Keywords: SDG 5, Muslim women, barriers, challenges, economic, social and political engagement

INTRODUCTION

Since women comprise half of the population in every nation, they deserve equal access to decision-making processes, social affairs, and especially in developing the economy. Their job is essential to the growth of our society. This is one of the Sustainable Development Goals established by the United Nations. SDG 5 seeks to offer women and girls equal rights and opportunities to live free of violence and discrimination, especially in their communities and workplaces.

Thus, the purpose of SDG 5 is to "achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls." The following targets of SDG 5 are related in this study: Target (5.1): Eliminate all forms of discrimination against all women and girls everywhere; (5.4) Recognize and value unpaid care and domestic work through the provision of public services, social protection policies, as well as the promotion of shared responsibility within the household and family, Ensure women's full and effective participation in political, economic, and public life, as well as equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making; and (5. a) Undertake reforms to give women equal rights to economic resources, including ownership and control over land and other forms of property, financial services, and inheritance.

Yet, the journey to equal representation has been protracted. Regardless of some growth through the years, women are still disadvantaged because of standards in society and culture, along with the lack of financial resources that limit them from fully engaging in decision-making and leadership roles. Perhaps one of the severe challenges that women are dealing with today is gender inequalities and acts of violence against them, particularly in the Muslim community. In the study of Aminudin (2023), he discovered that Muslim women deal with enormous

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challenges in their fight for recognition and voice in society, while the government weakens their sense of independence by restricting their right to decide for themselves.

Rahaman (2023) claimed that Islam grants women the right to everything, including political rights, and there is no compelling evidence to the contrary. Preventing Muslim women from voting has considerable harm to our community. The social, educational, economic, political, and material progress of any Muslim society will never be realized unless Muslim women actively participate (Racman, 2022). Male-dominated structures in communities severely limit Muslim women's ability to interact with and delegate power. Furthermore, fragmentation among women from various backgrounds limits their ability to express their voices and impact political peace processes effectively. Most Bangsamoro women's grassroots political participation has been significantly restricted by barriers such as the double burden of reproductive and productive labor, a lack of access to education, knowledge, and social networks, and limited connections with influential males (Hackansson, 2020).

Thus, this study covers the research gap by exploring and discussing the barriers and challenges that limit women's economic, social, and political engagement in the case of Muslim women in Baligatan, City of Ilagan. There are multiple pieces of literature focused on studying merely the political engagement of Muslim women, but inadequate studies were written tackling the support programs that empower Muslim women. This paved the way for the researchers to be curious about this study.

METHODS

A qualitative descriptive method was used in this study. The study was conducted in the Muslim community of Baligatan, Ilagan City, where most of the Muslim residents in the city reside. It included ten respondents, seven (7) Muslim women ages 18 - 55, (1) Barangay Captain, (1) SK Chairperson, and (1) the President of the Muslim community in Ilagan City. The sampling procedure employed in this study was snowball sampling.

A semi-structured interview guide was used to gather data. It consists of several critical questions based on this study's research questions and validated by an expert in qualitative research. Before interviewing the respondents, the researchers sought their approval and the barangay officials' approval through informed consent forms. Then, permission to conduct the interview was requested from the school authorities and the head or president of the Muslim community in the City of Ilagan. The procedures that were applied throughout the study are guided by ethical standards to ensure that the respondents' rights are protected.

Additionally, the researchers ensured that they prevented any possible harm to their respondents' profession, status, and credibility and that they were guided by the objectives. The interviews took place at a time convenient for the respondents. To make them comfortable, the interviews were conducted in casual settings. The data gathered was analyzed thematically. After the interviews, the data collected were transcribed and categorized into themes.

RESULTS

A brief description is given to provide a better understanding of the respondents' background. Seven of the respondents were female, while three were male. Their age ranges from 18 to 55. The Muslim women were four vendors: one high school student, one housewife, one barangay captain, one SK chairperson, and the Muslim President of Ilagan.

Economic, Social, and Political Engagement of Muslim Women in the Affairs of the City of Ilagan

Muslim women's engagement in economic affairs is their means of contributing economically. In Baligatan, Ilagan City, most Muslim women were doing business as their economic engagement. However, none of them are store owners. Respondent 2 said, "*Just by selling here at my employer's store*" (Respondent 2, Personal Communication, March 06, 2024). Relative to the study of Ilhaamie et al. (2014), it has been found that the different kinds of challenges experienced by Muslim women entrepreneurs in Malaysia include a lack of investments, a lack of customer demand, and a location problem. Selling is a decent and highly respected job. However, Muslim women must be given more space and resources to maximize their skills and potential for them to be advanced in their society. Even though some of the Muslim women have engaged in businesses, they find it challenging to have their businesses registered under their names due to inadequate resources.

As to social affairs, conducting and participating in occasional meetings is how Muslim women socialize within their community. It is all about woman-to-woman discussions and empowering each other. When they do this, they plan how to improve and benefit others. The same goes for the study of Noor (2018), who attended a mosque where Muslim women from a “sister group” were holding a “sister day” coupled with talks and prayers, gaining Islamic knowledge, and exchanging religious experiences. The purpose of this sister day was for Muslim women to nurture their connections with Allah and among themselves. These occasional meetings by Muslim women can be the beginning of a more active platform for them to empower each other. It is believed that in achieving a goal within a group, there must be a strong foundation and complete commitment coming from the entire group.

Regarding engaging in political affairs, Muslim women mentioned voting and decision-making. Voting is one of the aspects in which Muslim women can engage politically, meaning they practice their rights and have the freedom to choose their candidate/s during elections. However, most of the Muslim women in Baligatan vote depending on the choices of their husbands or the Muslim president. As per Respondent 2, she said, *“Yes, I have the freedom to choose my preferred candidate, but my choices depend on the candidate who is beneficial”* (Respondent 2, Personal Communication, March 06, 2024). Being critical when choosing a candidate to vote for is a big move. Thinking about the benefits is bigger.

In contrast, Respondent 3 stated, *“whoever my husband votes for, I should also vote for that particular candidate. He has more knowledge about it, that’s why I have no choice but to follow”* (Respondent 3, Personal Communication, March 6, 2024). Despite having the right to vote, some of the Muslim women are being swayed by the decisions of others. The data is congruent with the study of Finlay and Hopkins (2019), who have said that in Scotland, young Muslim women face barriers to political engagement due to gendered Islamophobia and discriminatory practices. Yet, several still participate in politics and civic affairs to clear up misconceptions and fight various forms of prejudice. Moreover, Male-dominated structures in communities severely limit Muslim women’s ability to interact with and delegate power.

In addition, Muslim women’s political engagement in decision-making. Most of them said they are included when there is decision-making in their community. However, some of the respondents conveyed different thoughts regarding this. Respondents 1, 2, 4, and 6 expressed that they are present whenever there is decision-making in their community. Respondent 5 shared, *“Yes, we can make suggestions, but men always have control”* (Respondent 5, Personal Communication, March 10, 2024). Being involved without being ultimately heard is pointless and unsatisfactory for the Muslim women in Baligatan. The data is supported by the study of Kubota and Takashi (2016). Male-dominated structures in communities severely limit Muslim women’s ability to interact with and delegate power.

Furthermore, fragmentation among women from various backgrounds limits their ability to express their voices and impact political peace processes effectively. Muslim women of Baligatan can be included in decision-making in their community. They are also open to conveying their suggestions. However, based on the findings, regardless of their engagement in decision-making and voicing out their opinions, they are not heard because of male dominance.

Overall, Muslim women engage economically, socially, and politically, but these engagements are part of their daily lives, and these efforts are insufficient to ensure their empowerment. On the bright side, these steps are essential in strengthening their engagement.

Barriers and Challenges Among Muslim Women in their Economic, Social, and Political Engagement

Discrimination

Five Muslim women from the study have experienced discrimination. The discrimination that they have experienced manifests through acts of bullying, marginalization, and prejudice. Respondent 3 said, *“There were times that people made fun of me because of my hijab. They said that I looked like a cancer patient”* (Respondent 3, Personal Communication, March 06, 2024). Muslim women become upset when they face out-group discrimination. Also, discrimination against them influences their engagement within and outside their community. The data gathered is supported by the study of Austria et al. (2023), saying that Muslim women are confronted with frustration when they encounter discrimination outside their religious community. The usual forms of out-group prejudice they encounter include being insulted about their religious symbols, such as hijabs, and being treated as

lesser human beings. Relatively, in the study of Balo et al. (2022), the majority of the study's respondents expressed having been labeled as "terrorists" by non-Muslims in their localities. Lingzi, also one of the participants, shared that when jeepney drivers notice them wearing a hijab, they refuse to stop because they are afraid.

Patriarchal Practices

Secondly, one of the barriers and challenges experienced by Muslim women is patriarchal practices. Five out of seven respondents claimed they could not choose their preferred candidates during elections. These Muslim women vote by the influence of their spouses or considering the decisions of their leader - the Muslim President. Respondent 6 expressed, "No, because men vote for us. Even though we women wanted to vote and make our own decisions, men will always take place" (Respondent 6, Personal Communication, March 10, 2024). No matter how much Respondent 6 desires to vote on her decisions, according to her, men will always have control. Though Muslim women are given full rights, Respondent 6 feels like they are restricted from doing so. The data above is supported by Rahaman (2023), who states that Islam grants women the right to everything, including political rights, and there is no compelling evidence to the contrary. Preventing Muslim women from voting has considerable harm to our community. Islam laws grant women the right to vote. Thus, male dominance is unfair. Muslim women endure a variety of discrimination and injustices that can lead to marginalization.

Inadequate opportunities for sources of living

Respondent 5 did not finish her studies. Hence, selling is her only source of income. As a result, she is having trouble finding a different job. Along with not being able to finish her education, she said that wearing her hijab is one of the reasons why she is being rejected. Congruent to the study of Ahmed & Gorey (2023), millions of Muslim women in the West have likely faced employment discrimination in the last generation. It appears that employers' negative impressions of the hijab are a substantial contributor to the comparatively higher levels of employment discrimination that Muslim women who wear the hijab encounter. Muslim women in Baligatan seek more opportunities to aid their finances adequately. But there were no other sources of living that they could do to sustain their lives. One significant factor is employment discrimination due to wearing a hijab, as mentioned by a respondent.

Lack of Self-confidence

It is challenging for the Muslim women in Baligatan to engage with the non-Muslims. Respondent 4 asserted, "I'm afraid because I am different from the others; most of them are Christian, and I am not" (Respondent 4, Personal Communication, March 10, 2024). Respondent 4 had experienced bullying in school, which caused her social anxiety that stopped her from engaging with other people, especially non-Muslims. Similarly, Braganza and Hodge (2023) have stated in their study that due to the difficulties encountered in interacting with non-Muslims, many Muslims ignore such engagements. This resistance might be attributed to feeling misunderstood, excluded, or unable to adequately express their religious ideas and perspectives. Having less confidence is one of the challenges that these Muslim women face when engaging socially. Theoretically, it could be rooted in the negative experiences that made them engage less, especially in social affairs. Muslim women in Baligatan are not highly involved in social affairs. One significant barrier to engaging socially, especially with non-Muslims, is a lack of confidence and being introverted.

Lack of Knowledge

According to Respondent 6, she cannot read or write, so she does not engage in political affairs. Although she wanted to, she claimed that her knowledge was limited. Similarly, Makuria (2018) stated that the Borana Muslim women in Mata'arba, Marsabit County, have a significant percentage of illiteracy. Cultural and other general issues that impact formal education among Muslim females in marginalized communities, such as Borana, are among the factors contributing to the high percentage of illiteracy among Muslim women. Indeed, lack of knowledge could impact someone's will and potential to engage politically; not having enough knowledge is one of the reasons why Muslim women are challenged in engaging with political affairs, especially when it comes to leadership.

Existing Activities and Practices of the Muslim Community in Achieving SDG 5

Most of the respondents shared that there were no existing activities and practices related to SDG-5 that the Muslim community does for its women. Thus, they hoped for the Muslim community to conduct initiatives to advance their rights and privileges as a woman. According to Respondent 4, "None, but I am hoping for an activity

that would empower us” (Respondent 4, Personal Communication, March 10, 2024). Efforts can be made to improve the livelihoods of Muslim women so they can overcome adversity and participate in community development.

On the other hand, the Muslim president mentioned, “*There is not yet. In fact, women are only support for us men here in the Muslim community*” (Respondent 8, Personal Communication, March 10, 2024). In Islam, women are deemed supporters of their husbands, and as a result, they find themselves limited in doing what they want to do. The statement above relates to the study of Sharif and Hina (2018) who asserted that social relations influence women’s lower or secondary status in patriarchal societies. Patriarchal society prioritizes men above women and, to some extent, limits their human rights. The statement indicates that “*men hold power in all important institutions of society*” and “*women are denied access to such power.*” In Pakistan, Muslim women’s political participation is limited due to the patriarchal and male-dominated society. Women’s mobility and movements were also severely restricted, although the sphere of politics required public relations and free movement.

Muslim women want a better place in society. Still, Muslim authorities have taken no immediate actions since it is clear that the Muslim community in the city of Ilagan lacks activities and practices that empower Muslim women with SDG 5. Although women are granted the same rights as men under the Quran and Islamic law, Muslim women are seen as their husband’s support, making them feel restricted in their rights. One factor contributing to the Muslim community’s lack of activities and practices is the emergence and tolerance of patriarchal practices within their immediate community.

Support Programs that Empower Muslim Women in their Economic, Social and Political Engagement

Madrasah

Two respondents of the study have mentioned that the “*Madrasah*” was presented as a support program that empowers Muslim women. Respondent 7 asserted, “*Only the madrasah which the DepEd implements. It is helpful, especially since I did not finish studying, which is why it is really helpful for the education*” (Respondent 7, Personal Communication, March 10, 2024). “*Madrasah*” is deemed valuable to Respondent 5, particularly regarding education, as she could not finish her studies.

Madrasah is a DepEd ALIVE program providing Arabic learning and Islamic values education. It is an Islamic education in the Philippines that is believed to coincide with the growth and coming of Islam. The Department of Education (DepEd) collaborates closely with the national government to develop and implement inclusive educational initiatives for Muslim students. This program is implemented for men and women. The DepEd Order (DO) No. 41, series of 2017, or “*Policy Guidelines on Madrasah Education in the K to 12 Basic Education Program,*” gives current suggestions for implementing Arabic Language and Islamic Values Education (ALIVE) in public schools around the country. It provides appropriate and relevant educational opportunities consistent with acceptable cultures, customs, traditions, and Muslim learners’ interests. Hoel (2016) notes that Women’s madrasahs in South Africa are alternative educational institutions dedicated to preserving Muslim identity, history, and devotion. These *madrasahs* play an essential role in conveying the concepts of gendered religious literacy and personhood to Muslim women in South Africa, molding their knowledge of Islam through the lens of gender and traditional standards.

As a result, *Madrasah* is one of the support programs that empower women in Baligatan, Ilagan City. Although this program is not specific to women, respondents found it particularly beneficial to their education. *Madrasah* also promotes their engagement and rights as Muslim women. However, half of the respondents have said there is not yet a program that empowers Muslim women in their overall engagement in the community. Although there is a program like *Madrasah*, it is still not enough for Muslim women to be empowered in their engagement in various affairs.

Ilagan Association for Women (ILAW)

ILAW is an association that works to unite all women in the city and receives assistance from the government for such events. Respondent 6 shared, “*I am a member of ILAW, but I don’t feel the presence of it, but sometimes I receive goods once a year*” (Respondent 6, Personal Communication, March 10, 2024). The data is supported by the study of Kubota and Takashi (2016). They mentioned that local government initiatives to promote female engagement frequently fail to fully grasp the needs and realities of women in local communities due to a lack of practical support networks, institutions, and local governance resources. To promote the development of local government capability, data collection, and analysis should be encouraged to identify local

women's needs and challenges and define community power relations. Muslim women in Baligatan may have been included in the government's programs for all women, but they could not feel thoroughly involved. Numerous support programs for all women are offered in Ilagan and other local government units. However, the findings suggest that Muslim women were overlooked in such programs, which gives them negative connotations about it.

DISCUSSION

Studies regarding Muslim women's identities are becoming increasingly prevalent. This research adds to the body of knowledge by focusing on Muslim women's barriers and challenges in their economic, social, and political engagement while incorporating Sustainable Development Goal 5 in empowering them. SDG 5 was implied in this study to strengthen the engagement of Muslim women further towards achieving gender equality.

The researchers determined that Muslim women in Baligatan have relatively minimal engagement in economic, social, and political affairs. Their financial, social, and political engagement must be improved to attain SDG 5. As a result, they want a more significant opportunity to grow and flourish in their community as they do what they want.

Findings suggest that doing business is the primary source of living for Muslim women in Baligatan, showcasing their economic contribution. Muslim women socially engage with one another through occasional meetings. And they engage in political affairs by voting and making decisions within their community, however limited.

Additionally, numerous factors influence their level of engagement in economic, social, and political affairs. The researchers concluded that the barriers and challenges that restrain Muslim women from engaging themselves in various affairs are discrimination, patriarchal practices, inadequate opportunities for sources of living, lack of confidence, and lack of knowledge. Also, they are still viewed as weak, basically as women, and unable to accomplish anything but serve their families. The researchers performed detailed interviews, which gave significant evidence of the barriers and challenges faced by these women.

Furthermore, the researchers also concluded that there were no existing activities and practices in the Muslim community to achieve SDG 5. *Madrakah* and *ILAW* emerged as support programs that empowered Muslim women in Ilagan, but these programs were still insufficient. Nonetheless, Muslim women are optimistic about becoming more advanced and empowered and desire support programs such as leadership, organizations, and training and seminars. The researchers found that if more support programs are implemented, these kinds of efforts will not only help to attain SDG 5 - gender equality but also minimize discrimination against Muslim women.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The findings of this study highlight the significant barriers and challenges that Muslim women in Baligatan, Ilagan City, face in their economic, social, and political engagement. Despite their efforts to contribute economically through business activities, engage socially through occasional meetings, and participate politically by voting and making community decisions, their overall engagement remains limited. The primary obstacles include discrimination, patriarchal practices, inadequate opportunities for livelihood, lack of self-confidence, and insufficient knowledge. These barriers are compounded by societal perceptions that view Muslim women as weak and confined to familial roles. Additionally, the study reveals a lack of existing activities and practices within the Muslim community aimed at achieving Sustainable Development Goal 5 (SDG 5) on gender equality. Although programs like *Madrakah* and the Ilagan Association for Women (ILAW) provide some support, they are insufficient to empower Muslim women fully. The implications of these findings suggest a need for more comprehensive support programs, including leadership training, organizational development, and seminars, to enhance the engagement and empowerment of Muslim women. Such initiatives would help achieve SDG 5, reduce discrimination, and foster a more inclusive community where Muslim women can thrive and contribute significantly.

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